
**ANALYSIS OF METHODS FOR FORMING LEXICOGRAPHIC
COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN STUDENTS IN TEACHING THE RUSSIAN
LANGUAGE**

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль лексиграфической компетенции в преподавании языка иностранным студентам, аспекты и пошаговые инструкции их формирования.

Ключевые слова: лексикография, лексическая компетенция, менталитет, глобальная компетенция, языковая компетенция.

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Abstract: The article discusses the role of lexigraphic competence in teaching language to foreign students, aspects and step-by-step instructions for their formation.

Keywords: lexicography, lexical competence, mentality, global competence, language competence

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Ona tili va chet tillarni kafedrasida o'qituvchi - stajyori

Annotatsiya: Maqolada chet ellik talabalarga til o'rgatishda leksigrafik kompetensiyaning o'rni, jihatlari va ularni shakllantirish bo'yicha bosqichma-bosqich ko'rsatmalar muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksikografiya, leksik kompetensiya, mentalitet, global kompetensiya, til kompetensiyasi.

The acquisition of lexico-semantic knowledge is crucial for foreign students learning the Russian language. Lexicographic competence, which encompasses the ability to effectively navigate and utilize dictionaries and other lexical resources, plays a significant role in language proficiency. This article aims to analyze various methods employed in teaching Russian to foreign students and their effectiveness in developing lexico-graphic competence.

1. Vocabulary Expansion through Contextual Learning:

One effective method is to expose foreign students to Russian vocabulary in context. This approach includes reading authentic texts, engaging in discussions, and using multimedia resources. By encountering words in meaningful contexts, students not only learn their meanings but also understand how they are used in different situations. This approach helps students develop a natural and intuitive grasp of vocabulary, enhancing their lexico-graphic competence.

2. Systematic Dictionary Training:

Integrating systematic dictionary training into language instruction can significantly contribute to developing lexico-graphic competence. Students should be introduced to different types of dictionaries, such as monolingual, bilingual, and specialized dictionaries. They should learn how to effectively search for words, interpret definitions, understand usage examples, and navigate various language resources. Practical exercises and assignments that involve dictionary use can reinforce these skills.

3. Corpus Linguistics and Electronic Resources:

The advent of technology has revolutionized language learning, offering unprecedented access to corpus linguistics and electronic resources. Corpus-based approaches provide learners with extensive data on word usage, collocations, and semantic associations. By utilizing online corpora and electronic dictionaries, students can enhance their lexico-graphic competence by exploring real language usage. They can also use language learning applications and websites that offer interactive exercises and vocabulary-building tools.

4. Vocabulary Games and Activities:

Incorporating vocabulary games and activities into language lessons can make the learning process more enjoyable and engaging. Word puzzles, flashcards, word association games, and vocabulary quizzes not only reinforce lexical knowledge but also foster lexical creativity and retention. By making vocabulary learning interactive and fun, students are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards lexico-graphic competence.

Developing lexico-graphic competence in foreign students learning the Russian language is a multifaceted process that requires a combination of effective teaching methods. Incorporating contextual learning, systematic dictionary training, corpus linguistics, electronic resources, and vocabulary games can significantly enhance students' ability to navigate and utilize lexical resources. By equipping foreign students with strong lexico-graphic competence, educators can empower them to become more confident and proficient in their Russian language skills.

5. Vocabulary in Authentic Situations:

Exposing foreign students to authentic situations where they can use and interact with Russian vocabulary is another effective method. This can include role-plays, simulations, and real-life scenarios. By practicing vocabulary in context, students develop a deeper understanding of how words are used, their nuances, and appropriate usage in different contexts. This approach helps bridge the gap between vocabulary learning and real-world application, strengthening lexico-graphic competence.

6. Word Formation and Word Families:

Exploring word formation processes and word families can greatly contribute to the development of lexico-graphic competence. By examining prefixes, suffixes, and word roots, students can expand their vocabulary exponentially. Understanding how words are formed enables students to make educated guesses about the meanings of unfamiliar words, leading to more effective dictionary use. Additionally, recognizing word families allows students to grasp related vocabulary, facilitating faster acquisition and retention.

7. Collocation and Phraseology:

Teaching foreign students about collocations and phraseology is essential for improving their lexico-graphic competence. Collocations are commonly occurring word combinations, while phraseology encompasses idiomatic expressions and fixed phrases. By focusing on collocations and phraseological units, students gain insight into natural language patterns, enhancing their ability to use words appropriately and accurately. Encouraging the use of collocation dictionaries and phraseological resources can further strengthen their lexico-graphic skills.

8. Individualized Vocabulary Learning:

Recognizing that each student has unique learning preferences and needs, individualized vocabulary learning should be incorporated. This approach involves identifying students' specific interests, goals, and areas where they struggle. By tailoring vocabulary exercises, assignments, and resources to their individual needs, students are more likely to engage with the material and develop their lexico-graphic competence at a personalized pace.

9. Integration of Cultural and Contextual Knowledge:

Understanding the cultural and contextual aspects of vocabulary is crucial for foreign students. Teaching the cultural connotations, social appropriateness, and pragmatic usage of words enables students to use vocabulary effectively in real-life situations. By integrating cultural and contextual knowledge into vocabulary instruction, students develop a deeper appreciation for the language and enhance their lexico-graphic competence in a culturally sensitive manner.

Incorporating vocabulary learning methods such as authentic situations, word formation, collocation, individualized learning, and cultural/contextual knowledge

can further enhance the development of lexico-graphic competence in foreign students learning Russian. By employing a diverse range of strategies, educators can create a dynamic and comprehensive learning environment that equips students with the necessary skills to navigate and utilize the Russian language effectively.

List of used literature:

1. Абдулвохидов Э. Педагогическая концепция писателей как средство обогащения педагогического процесса // Science and education Scientific journal ISSN 2181-0842 Volume 2, ISSUE 12, December 2021.

2. Багандова И.М. Лингвокультурологические проблемы перевода пословиц и поговорок даргинского языка на другие языки // Мир науки, культуры, образования. 2019. № 6 (79). С. 441-443.

3. Бахаева Л.М. Особенности этикетных моделей прощания в чеченской лингвокультуре// Российский гуманитарный журнал. 2019. Т. 8. № 2. С.153-160.

4. Бахаева Л.М. Языковая актуализация мужской картины мира в пословицах и поговорках чеченского языка// Современные проблемы науки и образования. 2015. № 1-1. С. 1209.

5. Баянова А.Т. Категория сравнения и способы ее выражения в фольклорном тексте: лингвокультурологический аспект (на примере калмыцких сказок в записи Г. Й. Рамстедта) // Oriental Studies. 2019. Т. № 41. С. 123-133.

6. Бец М.В., Лушпей А.А. Диалектная картина мира как лингвокультурологический феномен (на материале диалектизмов русского и немецкого языков) // Мир науки, культуры, образования. 2017. № 6 (67). С. 431-433.